

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Review Article

PERCEPTION OF THE EFFECTS OF WATER PIPE SMOKING ON OSTEOPOROSIS PATIENTS AMONG MEDICAL STUDENTS IN EASTERN REGION OF SAUDI ARABIA

¹Saud Nayef Aldanyowi, ²Ekram Sami Alkhalifah, ³Fatimah Alkhalifah, ⁴Anwar Alkhalifah, ⁵Faisal Faihan Alotaibi, ⁶Noor Abdulkarim Alqurqush, ⁷Shaikah Abdulaziz Alzarah, ⁸Muhannad Ismail Albader, ⁹Tariq Ali Alshaery, ¹⁰Munirah Mohammed Abdulaziz Al Shuaibi, ¹¹Hanin Jaber Mobarki

¹ Assistant Professor of orthopedic surgery, college of medicine, King Faisal university, Al Ahsa , Saudi Arabia

² College of medicine, medical intern at King Faisal University, Al Ahsa , Saudi Arabia

³ Department of family medicine at ministry of health, Al dammam , Saudi Arabia

⁴ Family medicine specialist at ministry of health , Al Dammam , Saudi Arabia

⁵ College of medicine, medical intern at Shaqra University, Shaqra, Saudi Arabia

⁶ College of medicine, medical student at King Faisal University, Al Ahsa ,Saudi Arabia

⁷ College of medicine, medical student at King Faisal University, Al Ahsa ,Saudi Arabia

⁸ College of medicine, medical intern at King Faisal University, Al Ahsa ,Saudi Arabia

⁹ PHC GP, Umm Al-Qura University Graduate Alqunfudah - Makkah Health Cluster

¹⁰ College of medicine, medical intern at King Faisal University, Al Ahsa ,Saudi Arabia

¹¹ College of medicine, medical student at Jazan university ,Jazan Saudi Arabia

Abstract:

Backgrounds: It is widely believed that waterpipe smoking (waterpipe, hookah, narghile, shisha) is not associated with health risks and it is less lethal than cigarettes smoking but several studies had documented the adverse effects of waterpipe smoking in health. Therefore, the present study aims to measure the level of perception among medical students at KFU on the effects of waterpipe smoking and the subsequent development of osteoporosis in eastern region of Saudi Arabia. It is believed water pipe smoking change the structure of bone which may lead to osteoporosis and Osteoporosis is bone disease that develops when bone mineral density and bone mass decreases , or when the quality or structure of bone changes .

Methods: A cross sectional was conducted among 377 medical students of KFU, between the age group 18 and above 24 years old. Data was collected using a self-administered questionnaire, the questionnaire was divided into three sections: the first section was about sociodemographic data. The second section consisted of three questions all related to smoking status and the third part consisted of true and false answers for 16 questions to test the respondent's knowledge and perception of waterpipe smoking and its effects on osteoporosis disease, the questions were including risk factors, diagnosis, and the management. The third part of the questionnaire, which is related to the knowledge, and had the following scoring criteria, 1 point for the correct answer and 0 point for the wrong answer and the total score out of 16 to 16 questions and the criteria was set as following groups, 1-4 poor, 5-9 moderate, 10-13 good, and 14-16 excellent knowledge. Data analyses were done using SPSS Version 20. The data was presented using chi-square for nominal data and T-test was used for numerical data. The significance level was set at $p \leq 0.05$ which is considered statically significant

Results: The results showed that Knowledge's scores among KFU medical student, 18.4% from the respondents had poor knowledge, 53.4 % had moderate knowledge, 26.6 % had good knowledge and 1.6% had excellent knowledge.

In conclusion, the majority of respondents had moderate knowledge of waterpipe smoking and osteoporosis. The findings may help to raise the awareness of the adverse effects of waterpipe smokers and the great risk for developing osteoporosis. Also, these results can be used for public health in water pipe prevention programs.

Keywords: osteoporosis, Knowledge, water pipe smoking, medical students

Corresponding author:

Saud Nayef Aldanyowi,
King Faisal University, Eastern region

QR code

Please cite this article in press *Saud Nayef Aldanyowi et al., Perception Of The Effects Of Water Pipe Smoking On Osteoporosis Patients Among Medical Students In Eastern Region Of Saudi Arabia., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2024; 11 (10).*

INTRODUCTION:

Osteoporosis is one of the serious metabolic bone diseases which is characterized by a gradual decline of bone mass and bone quality, which will lead to an increase of fracture risk and bone fragility. World health organization reports that **osteoporosis** is defined as a bone mass density that lies 2.5 standard deviations or more below the average value for young healthy women (a T- score of <-2.5 standard deviations) [1]. Osteoporosis affects a large number of people, of both sexes, all races, with the incidence increasing when the population gets older.

It had been reported that more than 8.9 million individuals with osteoporosis worldwide resulted in fractures annually, so every three seconds will result in osteoporotic fracture [2].

An estimated that Osteoporosis affects 200 million women worldwide - about one-tenth of women over the age of 60 years, one-fifth of women over the age of 70 years, two-fifths of women over the age of 80 years and two-thirds of women over the age of 90 years [3]. It is asymptomatic disease until fracture happened which causes complications and even death.

Smoking has been considered as a significant risk factor as it affects the body natural balance of bone resorption and bone formation, resulting in low bone mass density as the amount resorbed is not completely replaced so it will result in fractures as well. It had been reported by Law et al, [4] that cigarettes smoking is considered a major risk factor in decreasing bone density and causing a hip fracture. Another study which was done by Kenneth et al, [5] indicates that Smoking has a negative effect on bone health. Other Literate review been supporting that Smoking was associated with decreased hip bone mineral density in advanced age and developing bone diseases [4, 5, 6, 7, 8].

■ Smoking (waterpipe, hookah, narghile, shisha) is causing low bone density through different pathways, one of them is hormonal pathway which lead to changes in hormone household, which cause a

reduction of the level of parathyroid hormone and estrogen levels, however smoking will increase the level of cortisol and adrenal androgens, this will result in osteoporosis.

The second pathway that smoking reduces the level of Vitamin D in the body, which is essential for healthy

bone structure; Also, Smoking will increase free radicals and oxidative stress which eventually will affect bone resorption and people who are smokers are more likely to be affected from peripheral vascular disease, which will reduce blood supply to the bone and that will delay bone healing [9, 10].

Waterpipe smoking

Waterpipe smoking is the practice of burning tobacco and inhaling the smoke through a water pipe. The device consists of a head that is connected to the water bowl, with an attached hose and mouthpiece. The (head) bowl is partially filled with water and completely filled with tobacco on which is placed a piece of burning charcoal and the smoker inhales through the hose. It has been reported to be on an alarming increase in popularity among the youth [11]. It is estimated that the worldwide prevalence of daily waterpipe smoking (WPS) is around 100 million [12]. This form of smoking is prevalent in Lebanon among adolescents (13-15) years old, contrast to adults, it is most prevalent in Latvia which is a country in Europe [13]

It found that waterpipe smoking is prevalent in Al-Ahsa Saudi Arabia among male and female high school students [14]. Shisha (Arabic name for waterpipe tobacco) is considered the most popular type of water pipe tobacco [15]. *Shisha* comes in many flavors, including fruit and candy, so it tastes smooth and smells sweet making it an enjoyable and unrushed experience, very appealing to the youth. Many waterpipe smokers believe that WP tobacco smoking is less lethal than cigarette smoking, however, emerging studies indicate that both of them involve comparable health risks including nicotine dependence [16]. It had been reported that both types of smoking carry similar or higher risks than other forms of tobacco exposure [16,17].

Also, WHO reports that for cigarette smokers, it takes 5-7 minutes to inhale between 0.5 to 0.6 liters of smoke [15]. However, WPS sessions last longer as they take about 20-80 minutes during which between, 0.15 to 1 liter of smoke is inhaled. Therefore, WP smokers may be inhaling as much smoke during one WP smoking session as that of a cigarette smoker.

They reported that WPS has demonstrated its adverse health effects on many organs but most common organs are cardiovascular and respiratory systems such as coronary artery disease (CAD) and obstructive pulmonary disease with an increased risk to developing lung cancer [16]. WP tobacco smoking produces clear cardiovascular effects. The study indicated that a single 45 minutes of WPS, resulted in

an increased average heart rate [17]. Also, a recent study indicated that WPS lead to perinatal effects in smoking mothers and periodontal disease [14]. Earlier reports showed that Cigarette smoking is associated with reduced bone mineral density (BMD) and increased risk of fracture, thus identifying smoking as a risk factor to osteoporosis irrespective of whether or not it is WPS [15,18].

Although a recent study in Saudi Arabia indicated that one of the risk factors of osteoporosis is smoking [16]. literature is however silent on the relationship between the effect of WP smoking and osteoporosis in patients in Al-Ahsa region of Saudi Arabia.

Thesis statement:

This study aims to measure the level of perception among medical students at King Faisal University on the effects of waterpipe smoking and the subsequent development of osteoporosis in Al-Ahsa region of Saudi Arabia.

Pathophysiology of osteoporosis:

In response to trauma, Bone is continually remodeled. Bone remodeling occurs at different areas within the body which coupling process takes place when bone resorption is always followed by bone formation. Osteocalcin is the adjustment of growth orientation of BAp parallel to the collagen fibrils, which is important for bone strength to the loading direction of the long bone. The balance of the trimolecular control factor complex composed of osteoprotegerin (OPG), RANKL (osteoprotegerin ligand) and RANK maintains physiologic bone remodeling. In Osteoporosis, the skeletal mass will be reduced caused by resorbing is not completely replaced by bone formation. Under normal conditions, bone formation and resorption are in balance.

A change in either of increased bone resorption or decreased bone formation will cause osteoporosis. [3] There are many important factors which have a role contributing to the development of osteoporosis. The most common factors are aging and loss of gonadal function.

Risk factors of osteoporosis:

There are many risk factors such as aging (≥ 50 years), Female gender, White race, Genetic factors, such as a family history of osteoporosis, Thin body built or small stature, Menstrual irregularities such as Absence of menstruation or Late menarche, Early menopause, Postmenopausal state Physical inactivity, Use of certain drugs such as anticonvulsants, systemic steroids, thyroid supplements, heparin, chemotherapeutic agents), Alcohol abuse and

cigarettes smoking, Androgen or estrogen deficiency and Calcium deficiency[3,4,17].

Clinical types of osteoporosis

Patients are said to have primary osteoporosis which includes juvenile and idiopathic osteoporosis or secondary. Regarding the primary osteoporosis (juvenile) which it usually occurs in children or young adults with normal gonadal function and age group of 8-14 years old and it characterizes by sudden bone pain and/or a fracture following trauma. In the other hand, secondary osteoporosis occurs when there is an underlying cause or by using a specific type of drug. Renal Hypercalciuria is the most common cause of secondary osteoporosis. It should be mentioned that up to one-third of postmenopausal women, as well as premenopausal women, have an associated bone disorder [3,4,18,19].

Diagnosis of osteoporosis

The bone mineral density (BMD) test is the test that most commonly used to establish the diagnosis of osteoporosis or low bone density. One of the most used ways to measure BMD is DEXA-Scan (dual-energy X-ray absorptiometry or DXA) and it is considered the gold standard tool for diagnosing of osteoporosis. It uses a low energy X-ray to evaluate bone mineral density in the hip or spine.

BMD in osteopenia has a value between -1 and -2.5 SD below the young adult mean. It should be noted that osteoporosis BMD values are at least -2.5 SD or below. CT scans, X-rays, and ultrasounds are considered other diagnostic imaging tests that can be used to measure bone mineral density to detect osteoporosis besides DEXA scan [20,21].

Management of Osteoporosis

The most important targets in the management of osteoporosis are by preventing fractures and complications of osteoporosis and at the same time improving bone density.

Initially, non-pharmacological measures which include maintain the mobility and prevent falls and increase weight bearing exercise with lifestyle changes. Before we discussed the pharmacological therapy, there are some indications to initiate pharmacological therapy according to National Osteoporosis Foundation which include BMD T-scores below -2.0 by central DXA with no risk factors, bone mineral density T-scores below -1.5 by central DXA with one or more risk factors and lastly a previous vertebral or hip fracture [22,23].

Speaking about pharmacological medications which

are FDA-approved for the management of osteoporosis may be divided into anti resorptive medications which include estrogen, alendronate, risedronate, and calcitonin and anabolic agents, of which there is now only one-teriparatide, it should be noted that calcium and vitamin D supplements should be received the adequate dose of calcium and vitamin D for all patients with osteoporosis [24,25].

For postmenopausal osteoporosis, Alendronate can be used as first-line treatment every week. Raloxifene is considered an alternative choice for prevention of vertebral fractures or using of strontium ranelate as evidence treatment for vertebral and non-vertebral fractures. Teriparatide is another second-line therapy for established osteoporosis with fractures, it can be used when there is no response to the previous medications. It should be noted that calcitonin is rarely used and it should be only used in case of vertebral fractures when the patient complains of pain [26,27].

Prevention of Osteoporosis

In the past Osteoporosis is considered the normal aging process, but it is now it well known to be preventable and treatable. There are many interventions which can be used as primary or secondary prevention. Combined calcium and vitamin D intake is one of the strategies which increase bone density and strength and increase the maintenance level in the body. Other strategies include antiresorptive therapy, weight-bearing exercise, which is the most significant type of exercise which provides strength to prevent falls and improve posture and balance, quitting smoking, and avoidance of trip or fall hazards.

More study is needed to find the effects of Alcohol intake in osteoporosis patients, but a strong recommendation is for postmenopausal women to limit their alcohol intake according to current guidelines. According to latest research, the recommended amount of no more than 1 unit of alcohol daily for women and no more than 2 units daily for men [26 ,27,28].

Screening of Osteoporosis

Osteoporosis screening depends on bone mineral density measurement, usually by DEXA-Scan, which is then used to predict fracture risk. Hip BMD measurement by DEXA-Scan is considered to be the best diagnostic tool of hip fracture risk. There are Advantages which includes its noninvasive tool, low-level exposure to ionizing radiation. In the other hand, Disadvantages which include the inability to compare the results of one hospital to another. [26] According to the U.S. Preventive Services Task Force (USPSTF) recommends at least 2 years interval between

screenings to accurately measure BMD change [27].

Anatomy of the bone

- Long bone consisting of the **diaphysis, epiphysis, and metaphysis**. The diaphysis is composed of a tubular shaft that connects between the proximal and distal ends of the bone. **Medullary cavity** is like hollow region in the diaphysis and it filled with yellow bone marrow.
- The diaphysis walls consist of both types of dense and hard **compact bone**. Compact bone, this layer provides bone strength. One the inside of this bone, you would find a porous type of bone which is spongy or cancellous bone, this type of bone has irregular arrangements of tissue which allow maximum strength. The epiphysis is the rounded wider end at each end of the bones, which is filled with spongy bone. Red marrow fills the spaces in the spongy bone. Next is metaphysis, it is the narrow area which joins epiphysis with the diaphysis and it contains the **epiphyseal plate** (growth plate), which is a layer consisting of hyaline cartilage in a growing bone. At the age of 18 to 21 years (early adulthood) when the bone stops growing, the cartilage is converted to osseous tissue and the epiphyseal plate becomes an epiphyseal line.
- By cross-sectional of the bone, it consists of a thin layer which is called the Periosteum layer, it is composed of dense connective tissue. It consists of two layers, an outer which is a fibrous layer, made of main fibroblasts and an inner layer containing progenitor cells which become osteoblasts later on [19,20].

The process of Bone development

At the beginning of embryonic development, the embryo's skeleton is made of fibrous membranes and hyaline cartilage. At the end of the sixth or seventh week of embryonic life, the actual process of bone development, **ossification** begins. Intramembranous ossification and endochondral ossification are only two osteogenic pathways but in the end, the mature bone will form the same in spite of the pathway that produces it [19, 20].

➤ Intramembranous Ossification

The First pathway which is Intramembranous ossification which follows four stages. The first step is Mesenchymal cells group into clusters which form osteoblasts, and ossification centers form there. The second step which is osteoblasts will be a trap in Secreted osteoid, which then turned into osteocytes. Third step Trabecular matrix and periosteum form. Lastly, Compact bone develops superficial to the

trabecular bone and crowded blood vessels contract into red bone marrow [18, 19, 20].

➤ Endochondral Ossification

The Second pathway which is Endochondral Ossification. Endochondral ossification follows five stages. First one, Mesenchymal cells become chondrocytes that produce a cartilage model to form a bony skeleton. The second one, Blood vessels on the cartilage model condense osteoblasts which deposit a bony collar. The third one, Capillaries penetrate the cartilage and at the same time, it deposits bone inside the cartilage which will form primary ossification center. Forth one, Cartilage and chondrocytes continue to grow at ends of the bone while the medullary cavity remodels and forms. Then, after birth, Secondary ossification centers will develop. Finally, Hyaline cartilage remains at the epiphyseal plate and a joint surface and form as articular cartilage [19, 20].

MATERIAL AND METHOD:

➤ Study population and sample size

The proposed systematic study was carried out in King Faisal University in Al-Ahsa city of Saudi Arabia. The study was conducted during the month of February 2023. The study population included males and females medical students at King Faisal University, from the first year to internship year within the age group of 18 to above 24 years.

The exclusion criteria included males and females medical students which are not from KFU in Al-Ahsa city age below 18 years. The estimated sample size was 377 which was calculated using internet software for sample calculator **RaoSoft, Inc.** <http://www.raosoft.com/samplesize.html>

[29] , with 95% confidence interval and 5% margin error, and 50% response distribution.

➤ Measures and demographic

Demographic data of the respondents were taken and these data were divided into two levels of measurements, nominal which included (Gender, waterpipe smokers or not smokers) and numerical variables which included (time duration, number of smoking sessions per day). These variables were used for assessing the perception of the effects of water pipe smoking on osteoporosis.

➤ Data collection

Data was collected using a self-administered questionnaire (appendix 1). The questionnaire had been reviewed for content validity and then translated into Arabic and reliability test had been done.

The questionnaire was divided into three sections: the first section was about sociodemographic data such as age, gender, weight, marital status, and medical educational level. The second section consisted of three questions all related to a smoking status which were asked, the first question was ever heard of WPS, the second and the third question were whether the respondents was smoking or not, if yes which type of smoker they were.

The third part consisted of true and false answers for 16 questions to test the respondent's knowledge and perception of waterpipe smoking and its effects on osteoporosis disease, the questions were including risk factors, diagnosis and the management.

Scoring methods for the questionnaire:

The third part of the questionnaire which was related to the knowledge had the following scoring criteria, 1 point for the correct answer and 0 point for the wrong answer and the total score out of 16 to 16 questions and the criteria was set as following groups, 1-4 poor, 5-9 moderate, 10-13 good ,and 14-16 excellent knowledge.

➤ Statistical analysis

After collecting the data, data analyses were done using the statistical software program SPSS Version 20. The data was presented in the forms of frequencies and percentages were used for categorical data such as gender and marital status, while mean and standard

deviation were used for quantitative data such as age. The analytical test which used for comparison, including the T- test was used for numerical data and chi-square for nominal data. The significance level was set at $p \leq 0.05$ which is considered statically significant.

➤ Ethical clearance

Ethical clearance was obtained from the college of medicine of KFU as well as the local health authorities. The Printed structured questionnaire was distributed and written consent was obtained from participants with the full explanation of the study with their right if they refuse to participate and confidentiality was maintained throughout the study.

RESULTS:

A total of 377 respondents completed the questionnaire. 223 (40.8%) of the respondents were female, 154 (59.2%) were male. And the results are shown in Table 1, the minimum age was 16 and the maximum was above 24 years old. It was demonstrated that 72 (18.8%) of the subjects were 19 years old. Most of the respondents were from the first year medical school (26.8%)

followed by the interns (18.3%). It showed that interns of marital status were 18 (4.8%) of males and 63(16.7%) of females were married and the others were unmarried.

Table I: demographic table

Variables	Frequency (%)
Gender :	
Male:	154 (40.8%)
Female :	223 (59.2%)
Age : 18	18 (4.8%)
19	72 (18.8%)
20	57(15.1%)
21	33(8.8%)
22	31(8.2%)
23	56(14.9%)
24	49(13%)
Above 24	61(16.4%)
Marital status : Married :	18 (4.8%) male, 63 (16.7%) Female
Not married :	136(36.1%) male, 160(42.4%) Female
Academic year 1st	101 (26.8%)
year	47 (12.5%)
2rd year 3 rd	38 (10.1%)
year 4 th year 5 th	34 (9.0 %)
year 6 th year	27 (7.2%)
Intern	61 (16.2 %)
	69 (18.3%)

Table 2 illustrates the results on whether the respondents were smokers or non-smokers are shown in the table below, it was shown that the majority of them had been heard about waterpipe smoking 150 (9.8%) females, 124 (32.9%) males. It was demonstrated that only 25(6.6%) males, 11 (2.9%) females are smokers. Also, it was revealed that 341(90.4%) respondents were non- smokers. Furthermore, it showed 15 (4.0%) males and 10 (2.7%) females the respondents were cigarettes smokers. While 10 (2.7%) males, one (0.44%) female were waterpipe smokers. The results of our study reflect that was significant differences when correlated gender with smoking status (p value < 0.05).

Table II: Smoking status:

Variables	Frequency		P value	
	Male	female		
Have you ever heard about waterpipe smoking	Yes	124 (32.9%)	150 (39.8%)	0.036
	No	29 (7.3%)	74 (20 %)	
Are you smoker?	Yes	25 (6.6%)	11 (2.9%)	0.0001
	No	109 (28.9%)	206(54.6%)	
	Quit smoking	20 (5.3%)	6 (1.6%)	
If yes which type of smoker are you?	Cigarettes	15 (4.0%)	10 (2.7%)	0.001
	Waterpipe	10 (2.7%)	1(0.44%)	
	Both	0	0	

Table 3 illustrates the perception of the respondents of waterpipe smoking and subsequent developing of osteoporosis.

Table III: Illustrates the perception of the respondents regarding perception of waterpipe smoking and osteoporosis

Questions		N. (%)		P value
		Male	female	
Q1- Water pipe smoking has great effect on bone density?(True)	correct	17.0%	30.5%	0.062
	wrong	23.9%	28.7%	
Q2 -Waterpipe smoking has effect on fracture healing after trauma or surgery ? (True)	correct	18.3%	23.6%	0.783
	wrong	37.6%	20.5%	
Q3- The effects of waterpipe smoking on bone blood low that it will Reduce blood flow and increasing the risk of thrombosis?(true)	correct	22.3%	30.8%	0.714
	wrong	18.5 %	28.4%	
Q4 -Osteoporosis increase risk of bone fractures??(true)	Correct	32.6%	50.4%	0.397
	Wrong	8.2%	8.7%	
Q5- Osteoporosis is more common in women compared to men? (true)	correct	31.3	50.1%	0.016
	Wrong	9.6%	9.0%	

Q6- At the ago of 80 years most of the women will get osteoporosis? (true)	correct Wrong	32.1% 8.9%	47.2% 11.8%	0.238
Q7- Although osteoporosis more commonly affects older individuals, younger female athletes are at an increased risk for developing poor bone health and related complications?(True)	correct wrong	10.1% 44.6%	11.4% 33.9 %	0.262
Q8- Older women with osteoporosis may develop Impaired mobility Reduced productivity ,decrease socialization depression and Sleep disturbance?(True)	correct wrong	30.8% 10%	41.4% 17%	0.072
Q9 – anaerobic is the best exercise for osteoporosis?(False)	correct Wrong	15.6% 25.5%	18.3% 40.6%	0.359
Q10- The diagnostic method for osteoporosis is Dexa scan?(true)	Correct Wrong	22.3% 18.5%	34.2% 25.0%	0.076
Q11- T score Between -1.0 and -2.5 means indicate that	correct wrong	17.0% 23.8%	21.0% 38.2%	0.208
Q12- there is a significant effect of waterpipe smoking on overall fracture risk – in particular Spine, Hip and wrist. (True)	correct Wrong	27.3% 13.6%	34.5% 24.6 %	0.034
Q13- Why Are Bones Affected by waterpipe Smoking because Nicotine constricts blood vessels. (True)	correct Wrong	16.4% 24.3%	16.7% 42.6%	0.006
Q14-Water pipe Smoking is associated with low bone density through various pathways , one of them has been linked to Changes in hormone household, leading to a decrease in Parathyroid hormone and estrogen? (True)	correct Wrong	8.8% 30.8%	12.5% 47.9%	0.925
Q15- The levels of (CO and tar) produced by a single waterpipe use episode are greater compared to than those found in the smoke a single cigarette? (true)	correct Wrong	24.9% 15.9%	27.1% 32.1%	0.000 1
Q16- waterpipe smoker’s inhale compared to one cigarette is Less than 50%? (False)	correct Wrong	18.3% 22.5%	22.8% 36.4%	0.310

Table IV: demonstrates the Knowledge’s scores among KFU medical student, it showed 18.4% from the respondents had poor knowledge, 53.4 % had moderate knowledge, 26.6 % had good knowledge and 1.6% had excellent knowledge. Table IV. Knowledge’s scores:

Knowledge’s scores	NO. (%)
Poor Knowledge	18.4%
Moderate Knowledge	53.4%
Good Knowledge	26.6%
Excellent Knowledge	1.6%

Figure 1: show Knowledge’s scores of the perception of our respondents regarding perception of waterpipe smoking and osteoporosis.

Figure 2 show the mean of the total score of 16 is directly proportional to the academic year until the sixth year then it is declining in the internship year.

Figure 2: show the comparison of the mean of the total score of 16 questions to the academic year

DISCUSSION:

The present study aim is to measure the level of perception among medical students at King Faisal University on the effects of waterpipe smoking and the subsequent development of osteoporosis in Al-Ahsa region of Saudi Arabia. This study showed that the majority of the respondents had moderate knowledge 53.4% regarding the perception of waterpipe smoking and osteoporosis. This study showed similar results with other study which was done, in general population of Saudi Arabia. [30] Overall, there was no significant differences between genders. Regardless of the gender, only 1.6% revealed excellent level of perception, while 26.6% revealed good knowledge regarding osteoporosis and waterpipe smoking.

Only, 18.4 % showed poor or low knowledge, and this explains why they had the poor score, because most of the participants who had score poor were from the first year of medical school. As figure 2 showed that total score of 16 is directly proportional to the academic year until internship year then it is declining. This reflects inadequate knowledge of the interns compared to other academic year.

Most of the respondents were able to answer the questions related to osteoporosis risk factors (such as bone fractures 83%, women 81.4%, and aging 79.3%). Surprisingly, fewer participants were able to answer other factors such as young female athletes are at greater risk of osteoporosis and other complication (21.5%), and waterpipe smoking is associated with

changes in hormone threshold leading to decrease in estrogen and parathyroid (21.3%). The results had opposite finding from other study by Muhammad et al, [31] which was conducted in Pakistan that measured the perception regarding osteoporosis among female medical school entrants. Their study confirmed that only 8.0% of the respondents had a good score regarding perception about osteoporosis whereas majority of the respondents (49.0%) scored poor. [31]

Other study which was conducted by Jin et al, [32] in South Korea that measured the awareness of severe osteoporosis among medical doctors in South Korea: the study revealed that 89% of the doctors had concerns about treatments for severe osteoporosis but there is a lack of the awareness regarding the diagnosis. [32] Similar result of the present study which was conducted by Muhammad et al, [33] in Pakistan about perception of Nurses Regarding Prevention of Osteoporosis among Nurses of Jinnah Hospital and General Hospital, the finding showed that Nurses have moderate perception about risk factor and prevention of osteoporosis which supports the present study [33].

There are some limitations to this study. The population of the present study was limited because only one medical school were included, because the present study explored the awareness among medical students of KFU only.

Moreover, perception about osteoporosis was assessed

through assessment of possible risk factors and pathophysiology and some preventive measures, so the survey encourages guessing and might not be a true reflection of the respondents' knowledge regarding osteoporosis and waterpipe smoking.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS:

In conclusion, the majority of respondents had moderate knowledge of waterpipe smoking and osteoporosis. waterpipe smoking is very common in the eastern region so the present study highlights the need for health education about the effects of waterpipe smoking on osteoporosis, which targeted to general population of Saudi Arabia and not only the medical students.

Moreover, the present study reflects that more research is needed not only spreading the awareness about waterpipe smoking and subsequent developing of osteoporosis among medical students but also for promoting preventative measures for the osteoporosis, which include educating people about the vitamin D, calcium intake and physical activity.

REFERENCES:

- 1- Assessment of fracture risk and its application to screening for postmenopausal osteoporosis-report of a WHO study group. World Health Organ Tech Rep Ser. 1994; 843:1–129.
- 2- Johnell O and Kanis JA (2006) An estimate of the worldwide prevalence and disability associated with osteoporotic fractures. *Osteoporos Int* 17:1726.
- 3- Matthew B Dobbs, C. (1999). Osteoporosis: The Increasing Role of the Orthopaedist. 19: 43–52.
- 4- AK, L. (1997). A meta-analysis of cigarette smoking, bone mineral density and risk of hip fracture: recognition of a major effect. *Oct 4; 315(7112):841-6.*
- 5- Kenneth D. Ward, R. (2017). A Meta-Analysis of the Effects of Cigarette Smoking on Bone Mineral Density. 2001 May 68(5): 259–270.
- 6- El-Zaatari, Z. M., H. A. Chami, and G. S. Zaatari. 'Health Effects Associated With Waterpipe Smoking'. *Tobacco Control* 24.Supplement 1 (2015): i31-i43.
- 7- Yoon V, Maalouf N, Sakhaee K. The effects of smoking on bone metabolism. *Osteoporosis International*. 2012;23(8):2081-2092.
- 8- K A Hollenbach, T. (2019). *Cigarette smoking and bone mineral density in older men and women*. 83(9): 1265–1270.
- 9- TH, K. (2005). *Smoking and hormones in health and endocrine disorders*. 152(4):491- 9.
- 10- metabolism. *Eur J Clin Nutr* 1999; 53(12):920–926.
16. Duthie GG, Arthur JR, James WP. Effects of smoking and vitamin E on blood antioxidant status. *Am J Clin Nutr* 1991; 53(4 Suppl):1061S–1063S.
- 11- Kanis JA. (2007)World Health Organization Scientific Group .Assessment of osteoporosis at the primary health-care level. Technical Report.
- 12- Akl E, Gunukula S, Aleem S, Obeid R, Jaoude P, Honeine R et al. The prevalence of waterpipe tobacco smoking among the general and specific populations: a systematic review. *BMC Public Health*. 2011;11(1):244.
- 13- Al Moamary M, Al Ghobain M, Al Shehri S, Alfayez A, Gasmelseed A, Al-Hajjaj M. The prevalence and characteristics of water-pipe smoking among high school students in Saudi Arabia. *Journal of Infection and Public Health*. 2012;5(2):159-168.
- 14- Gatrad R, Gatrad A, Sheikh A. Hookah smoking. *BMJ*. 2007; 335(7609):20-20.
- 15- CVA,K.(2017). *Journal of Orthopedics & Bone Disorders*, 1(7).
- 16- Maziak W, Taleb Z, Bahelah R, Islam F, Jaber R, Auf R et al. The global epidemiology of waterpipe smoking. *Tobacco Control*. 2014;24(Supplement 1):i3-i12.
- 17- Cobb C, Ward K, Maziak W, Shihadeh A, Eissenberg T. Waterpipe Tobacco Smoking: An Emerging Health Crisis in the United States. *am j hlth behav*. 2010;34(3):275-285.
- 18- Shafagoj Y, Mohammed F, Hadidi K. Hubble-bubble (water pipe) smoking: levels of nicotine and cotinine in plasma, saliva and urine. *Int Journal of Clinical Pharmacology and Therapeutics*. 2002;40(06):249-255.
- 19- Marieb, E. and Hoehn, K. (n.d.). *Human anatomy & physiology*.
- 20- Gulya, A. and Schuknecht, H. (2007). *Gulya and Schuknecht's anatomy of the temporal bone with surgical implications*. New York [u.a.]: Informa Healthcare.
- 21- Johnell O, Kanis J. Epidemiology of osteoporotic fractures. *Osteoporos Int* 2005;16: S3–S7.
- 22- Al-Otaibi H. Osteoporosis Health Beliefs, Knowledge and Life Habits among Women in Saudi Arabia. *OJPM*. 2015;05(06):236-243.
- 23- RP, H. (1998). *Pathophysiology of osteoporosis*.;27(2):255-65.
- 24- Raef H, Frayha HH, El-Shaker M, Al-Humaidan A, Conca W, Sieck U, et al. Recommendations for the diagnosis and management of osteoporosis: A local perspective. *Ann Saudi Med*. 2004;24:242–52.
- 25- Foundation National Osteoporosis. Physician's guide to prevention and treatment of

- osteoporosis. Washington, D.C, National Osteoporosis Foundation; 2003.
- 26- Foundation National Osteoporosis. America's Bone Health: The State of Osteoporosis and Low Bone Mass in Our Nation. National Osteoporosis Foundation; 2002.
 - 27- Burge R, Dawson-Hughes B, Solomon DH, Wong JB, King A, Tosteson A. Incidence and economic burden of osteoporosis-related fractures in the United States, 2005– 2025. *J Bone Miner Res* 2007;22: 465–475
 - 28- Cummings SR, Bates D, Black DM. Clinical use of bone densitometry: scientific review. *JAMA* 2002;288:1889–1897 Erratum in: *JAMA* 2002;288:2825.
 - 29- Raosoft.com. (2019). *Sample Size Calculator by Raosoft, Inc.*. [online] Available at: <http://www.raosoft.com/samplesize.html>.
 - 30- Alghamdi, M. and Mohammed, A. (2018). Knowledge and Awareness of Osteoporosis among Saudi Physicians and Nurses: A Cross-Sectional Study. *Open Access Macedonian Journal of Medical Sciences*, 20; 6(5): 913–916.
 - 31- Bila M.(2017) Knowledge, beliefs and practices regarding osteoporosis among female medical school entrants in Pakistan. 16: 6.
 - 32- Jin HwanKim.(2016) Perception of severe osteoporosis amongst medical doctors in South Korea: Awareness, impact, and treatment. Volume 2, Issues 1, P 45-63.
 - 33- Riaz M (2017)To Assess the Knowledge of Nurses Regarding Prevention of Osteoporosis among Nurses of Jinnah Hospital and General Hospital Lahore Pakistan. Vol. 4, Issue-3: 202-209.

Appendix 1

Questionnaire regarding Perception of the effects of water pipe smoking on osteoporosis among KFU medical students in Al-Ahsa city of Saudi Arabia

You are invited to take part in this study. This study requires you to complete this survey and I will deal with your answers confidentially and it will be used only for purpose of this study and no names are required.

- Are you agree to participate in this study

yes NO

Age

- 18
- 19
- 20
- 21
- 22
- 23
- 24 and above

2- Gender

- Male
- Female

3- Marital status

- Married
- Not married

4- Which year of medical school?

- First
- Second
- Third
- Forth
- Fifth
- Sixth
- Intern

5- Have you ever heard about waterpipe smoking?

- Yes
- No

6- Are you a smoker?

- No I had never smoke.
- Ex-smoker
- Yes ,Current smoker

7- if yes which type of smoker are you?

- water pipe**
- cigarettes**
- both**

8- Does water pipe smoking have a great effect on bone density?

- False**
- True**

9- Does waterpipe smoking have an effect on fracture healing after trauma or surgery?

- True**
- False**

10- The effects of waterpipe smoking on bone blood flow it will Reduce blood flow and increasing the risk of thrombosis?

- True
- False

11- Does osteoporosis increase the risk of bone fractures?

- True
- False

12- Osteoporosis is more common in women compared to men?

- True
- False

13- At the age of 80 years most of the women will get osteoporosis?

- True
- False

14- Although osteoporosis more commonly affects older individuals, younger female athletes are at an increased risk for developing poor bone health and related complications. True or false?

- True
- False

15- Older women with osteoporosis may develop impaired mobility, reduced productivity, Decrease socialization, Depression and Sleep disturbance?

- True
- False

16- Anaerobic is the best Exercise for osteoporosis?

- True
- False

17- The diagnostic method for Osteoporosis is Dexa scan?

- True
- False

18-T-score Between -1.0 and -2.5 means indicates that you have osteoporosis?

- True
- False

19- There is a significant effect of waterpipe smoking on overall fracture risk – in particular hip ,spine and wrist bone ?

- True
- False

20- Why Are Bones affected by waterpipe Smoking because Nicotine constricts blood vessels?

- True
- False

21- Water pipe Smoking is associated with low bone density through various pathways, one of them has been linked to changes in hormone household, leading to a decrease in Parathyroid hormone and Estrogen ?

- True
- False

22- The levels of (CO and tar) produced by a single waterpipe use episode are greater compared to than those found in the smoke a single cigarette?

- True
- False

23- Waterpipe smokers inhale Less than 50% compared to one cigarette?

- True
- False